

Career Competency, Self-Efficacy, and Organizational Commitment at Work

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Career Competency describes the knowledge base and performance standards required to successfully complete a job or hold a position and employee competence is characterized by the extent of employee knowledge, skills, traits, and behaviour which can be technical, interpersonal skills related or business oriented. Also, Self-efficacy of an employee is one of the most influential aspects of self-knowledge which influences the individual in determining the actions to be taken to achieve a goal. Therefore, in order to survive and to achieve its goals, organizations must focus more on developing the competency skills, efficiency and effectiveness of its manpower by increasing their level of commitment for accelerated growth and development of the organization.

Research Aims: This paper attempts to analyze the constructs of the conceptual model (career competency, self-efficacy and organizational commitment) and to determine differences amongst respondents with respect to Organizational Commitment based on chosen demographic variables (gender, age, years of experience and monthly income).

Design/Methodology/Approach: Sample Size: Primary data was collected from 349 male and female employees working in public and private sector organisations through a structured questionnaire on a five-point Likert's scale.

Tools and Techniques: Statistical tools like weighted mean, t test and ANOVA are employed and Convenience sampling technique was adopted for the study.

Key Findings: The weighted mean results revealed that out of the six factors of Career Competency 'Reflection on Motivation' has emerged as the most important factor followed by 'Reflection on Qualities'. t test results revealed that female respondents were more committed to their organization than the male employees. ANOVA result indicate that there exist significant differences among the respondents based on the chosen demographic variables namely, age, years of work experience and monthly income with respect to Organizational Commitment.

Paper Type: Analytical research

Keywords: Career Competency, Self-Efficacy, Affective Commitment, Normative Commitment, Continuance Commitment

1. INTRODUCTION:

Career Competency is the ability of an employee to execute or perform a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and it is supported by the work attitude demanded by their job. There is the need for each organisation to identify the competency skills of their work force and involve them in career developmental activities and techniques in order to help them to achieve their career goals and thereby the organisational goals also. Such strategies make the employees become more committed towards their organisation, for which purpose of Self –Efficacy acts a predictor.

Self-efficacy is the belief of an individual to achieve success utilising their competence skills and abilities which affect their performance in a wide spectrum of life including the workplace. In workplace, employees who possess a high level of self-efficacy are more likely to exert greater efforts even in difficult situations and thereby produce more favourable outcomes. Since highly committed employees significantly perform better in their organizations, it is necessary to study self-efficacy as a predictor of organizational commitment.

Why do some people like to spend their entire lives working for the same company? What keeps a person with the company? What characteristics are shared by employees who feel they would not wish to leave the company? These questions are all centred on organisational commitment. An employee is a member of a collective group and this invisible tie between an employee and a collective group has to be studied when one is interested in organizational commitment. The degree to which a person is attached to a particular organisation varies, and there are many different factors that may underlie this attachment, such as affection, a conscious decision, or a habit. (Jokivuori 2002). It is crucial to be able to retain people for a long time since the firm invests a lot of time on them and resources. Commitment comes into play in this process and thus it is an interesting focus of study, especially when there exists compulsion to gain competitive advantage, in order to survive. Therefore, this study attempts to examine Career Competency and Self-Efficacy (independent variables) as predictors of Organizational Commitment (dependent variable).

2. CAREERCOMPETENCY :

When evaluating an organization's performance, top management outcomes are increasingly attributed to human resources and their competencies rather than to physical resources. As a result, one of the organization's top focuses is on the development of the competency skills of their current workforce that would enable an employee to successfully operate in a business and economic environment that is always changing. Drucker (1985), a pioneer in management literature, defined competence at the individual level as the capacity of a

person to provide outstanding performance in tasks that are entrusted to them. Competence is an underlying attribute of a person, goals, traits, abilities, aspects of image or social role, and information that a person is able to employ (Boyatzis, Stubbs, and Taylor, 2002). Spencer & Spencer, (1993) gave the following definition of competence: it is the capacity to perform successfully in terms of qualification, skills, and knowledge; to have the authority to accomplish something; and highly qualified awareness. It is an independent variable in this study measured using six factors namely 'Reflection on Motivation', 'Reflection on Qualities', 'Networking', 'Self-Profiling', 'Work Exploration' and 'Career Control' with three statements each.

3. SELF EFFICACY :

Self-efficacy can affect how employees think, feel, motivate themselves, and act according to the rules, so that in the end it will create organizational commitment and employee performance. Yokoyama, (2019) Issa, (2016). Sarinah et al. (2018) and Zeb and Nawaz (2016) proved that self-efficacy can improve a person's quality and psychosocial level. Arya et al (2012) found that a positive relation exists between self-efficacy and organizational commitment. Bandura (2000) defines self-efficacy as ability to perform a task or action needed to achieve a particular result. Self-efficacy is the belief that someone can control the situation and get positive results (Zulkosky 2009). High self-efficacy, according to Robbins and Judge (2007), improves one's odds of succeeding at a task. People with low self-efficacy give up under trying circumstances, but those with strong self-efficacy work harder to overcome obstacle. In behavioural sciences, this self-assurance thrust or self-belief is known as self-efficacy. Sinha et al [2002] revealed that organizational commitment is positively related to self-efficacy. Self-Efficacy is the confidence that one can develop the knowledge to handle novel or difficult tasks, and the ability to deal with changes in performance. When people recognise their own self-efficacy, it allows them to establish objectives, try to attain them, resolve difficulties and recover from failure and discontent. It might be seen as a positive outlook or useful strategy to handle difficulties. According to Csikszentmihalyi's (1997) theory, a person's confidence that he will succeed, motivates him to do the assigned activity successfully. Fitzgerald (1991) emphasizes that self-efficacy is a self-perception of how well one can function in certain situations. Sometimes people overestimate their ability to perform jobs that they are not truly capable of. Self-efficacy is a concept that Bandura (1986) created and defined in his Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) as a person's confidence in their ability to complete a task in a specific circumstance. As a result, they have to deal with difficulties. It is an independent variable in this study which is measured using five statements.

4. ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT :

When it comes to organisational performance, organisations are experiencing significant problems from downsizing, re-engineering, or restructuring to an explosion of information and an increase in the diversity of the workforce. Corporate commitment is one of the instruments managers can use to examine employees' identification with organisational goals and loyalty tying them to their workplace (Zayas-Ortiz et al., 2015). According to reports, certain employee behaviours are considered to be behaviours for organisational effectiveness. These behaviours include employees joining and remaining with the organisation, fulfilling specific role requirements, and taking initiative and acting spontaneously in ways that go beyond prescribed

roles (Shahid and Azhar, 2013). Institutions of higher education are among the public enterprises where these changes are anticipated to occur (Nordin, 2012). In studies of the workplace, organisational commitment has garnered considerable attention. This is because it is well acknowledged that this factor can play a significant role in determining the efficacy and performance of an organisation. If opportunities are unavailable, they may emotionally or mentally withdraw from the organisation. Thus, organisational commitment is an important attitude in assessing employees' overall contribution to the organisation. Over the past several decades, both researchers and employers have been very interested in understanding what commitment is, what causes a sense of commitment, and what those devoted feelings might foretell. Employers can improve workplace efficiency and productivity by understanding how to encourage a sense of commitment among their employees and understanding the behavioural outcomes of that commitment. Although organizational commitment has different classifications, this study has used the affective, normative and continuance commitment of Meyer and Allen (1997) and it is a dependent variable in this study, measured using three statements.

4.1 Affective Commitment:

Affective commitment is defined as people's satisfaction with the organisation and their decision to be the member of the organisation. In other words, affective commitment is the level of devotion that employees have towards their organisation.

4.2 Normative Commitment:

Normative commitment indicates the value of employees to the company. High-level normatively committed employees believe they should stay with the organisation. Employees feel devoted to the organisation because of the organization's culture and work ethic, which results in normative commitment.

4.3 Continuance Commitment:

The need to remain in the company is outlined by the continuity promise because leaving the company could result in costs for the organisation. As they do not have any other job alternatives and do not want to change their jobs, employees prefer to stay in the organization. In conclusion, employees with strong affective commitment stay in the organization because they want to, those with strong continuance commitment because they need to, and those with strong normative commitment because they feel they ought to do so.

5. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

5.1 Career Competency:

Competence is an ability to execute or perform a job or task that is based on skills and knowledge and is supported by the work attitude demanded by the job. Ahdan et al., 2019; Ansar et al., 2019; Tamsah et al., 2020 concluded that there was a positive and significant influence of competence on organizational commitment. Fadli (2012), Rommi (2017), Fakrul (2017) showed that career competency had a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Research conducted by Wibowo (2006), Hidayat (2012) and Nurhidayatul (2017), stated that career competency had a positive and significant impact on organizational commitment.

Career Competence is an ability to carry out or perform a job or task based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job (Wibowo, 2016). Meanwhile, research conducted by Jaya (2014) and Sari (2010) found career development did not have a significant effect on organizational commitment. Competence as a person's ability to produce at a satisfactory level in the workplace proved that knowledge and skills possessed or needed by any individual enabled them to perform their duties and responsibilities effectively and improve the quality standards of Professional employment (David Mc. Clelland, 1997).

5.2 Self-Efficacy:

Adewale et al. (2017) defined self-efficacy as people's decision about their capability to carry out a specific duty or task. It is the skill to achieve a desirable or intended result, a belief on capacity to execute behaviors needed to be successful for specific performance achievements (Aggarwal, 2014). Researchers also suggest that people with higher self-efficacy are able to solve difficult situations in a much better manner than those with low self-efficacy (Heuven et al., 2006; Tsang et al., 2012). In a study done by Arya et al [2012], it was found that a positive relation exists between self-efficacy and organizational commitment. Maddux (2002) has described self – efficacy as “what I believed, I can do with my skill under certain conditions”. Bandura (1997) defined self-efficacy as “people's beliefs in their capabilities to produce desired effects by their own actions.

5.3 Organisational Commitment:

According to Umam (2018): "Commitment in organizations is a psychological structure which is characteristic of the relationship between members of the organization and has implications for individual satisfaction to continue their membership in the organisation". Edison et al., (2018) posits that: "Commitment is a form where employees have involvement, accept existing environmental conditions and strive to excel and serve". Meyer and Allen in Umam (2018) formulated three dimensions of commitment, namely, Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment, and Normative Commitment. Akram, Afzal, and Ramay (2017) argued that commitment is the attitude of the employees in the organization and it can be measured by many factors. In addition, Wibowo, (2016b) defines that: "Organizational commitment is the feeling of identification, loyalty and involvement expressed by the worker towards the organization or unit in the organization". Suparjo and Darmanto, (2015) also found that commitment increases if employees believe in the organization values. Fu and Deshpande (2013) did not have the same opinion of the above researchers, because they found that the commitment is not measured by the level of acceptance of the changes, but it is measured by the level of employees' identification in the organization. Kim (2013) defined organizational commitment, as the relationship that the employees build with their organization during their stay. Vakola and Nikolaou (2005) argued that when the individuals enter the organization they expect to have what they need and when the organization provides the individual with their needs they will be committed to the organization. Also, they defined commitment in three dimensions: the first one is the acceptance of the organization values and standards, the second one is the desire of employees to do their best and put in extra efforts to achieve organizational goals and the last one is the strong desire to be a member who strongly belongs to the organization. Based on the understanding of the

experts above, it can be concluded that commitment is a form of accepting the company environment by employees so that they can contribute and serve the company to achieve its goal.

6. RESEARCH GAP :

Focus on organisational commitment as a HRD strategy, and the increased attention given to the role of emotional attachment to organizations warrants a modern review of organizational commitment literature with a focus on affective, normative and continuance commitment (or emotional and attitudinal) organizational commitment as termed by Meyer & Allen (1984). Thus, this article intends to serve as a review, analysis, and synthesis of the literature on organizational commitment and its antecedents. The study may also serve to provide direction for future researchers and practitioners studying organizational commitment and more specifically with respect to the three different kinds of organisational commitment namely, affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment. Although numerous researches have been done to find out the relationship between self-efficacy, career competency and organizational commitment, extremely few studies have been done investigating these two psychological constructs in public and private sectors of India. Therefore this paper will examine the group differences based on chosen demographic variables namely gender, age, years of work experience and monthly income of the respondents between the independent variables (Career Competency, Self-Efficacy) and Organizational Commitment (dependent variable).

7. SCOPE OF THE STUDY :

The scope of this study is to examine the phenomena related to Career Competency, Self-efficacy and Organisational Commitment among public and private sector employees. It will help in identifying the differences that exists among these variables. The study will provide a foundation for exploring the impact of these variables on employees and would further help the organisations to design the strategies to increase the level of organisational commitment.

8. OBJECTIVES:

- (i) To analyze the constructs of the conceptual model.
- (ii) To determine group differences amongst respondents with respect to Organisational Commitment based on chosen demographic variables (gender, age, years of experience, monthly income).

9. CONCEPTUAL MODEL AND HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY :

Fig. No.1: CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE STUDY

10. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY :

First Hypothesis (t test):

Null Hypothesis (H01): There is no significant difference between male and female respondents with respect to Organisational Commitment.

Alternative Hypothesis (HA1): H01 is not true.

Second Hypothesis (ANOVA):

Null Hypothesis (H02): There is no significant difference among the respondents of different age groups with respect to Organisational Commitment.

Alternative Hypothesis (HA2): H02 is not true.

Third Hypothesis (ANOVA):

Null Hypothesis (H03): There is no significant difference among respondents with varying years of work experience with respect to Organisational Commitment.

Alternative Hypothesis (HA3): H03 is not true.

Fourth Hypothesis (ANOVA):

Null Hypothesis (H04): There is no significant difference among the respondents belonging to different income groups with respect to Organisational Commitment

Alternative Hypothesis (HA4): H04 is not true.

11. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Sample Size & Technique: The sample consists of 349 male and female employees working in public and private sector organisations. Convenience sampling technique was adopted for the study.

Data Source: Primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire on a five-point scale Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree.

Statistical Tools: The various statistical tools like weighted mean, t test and ANOVA are employed to carry out the study using SPSS 21.

12. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Demographic Profile of the respondents:

Out of 349 respondents, 51.8% (181) of the respondents are male, 42.4% (148) belong to the age group of 35-45 years, 38.9% (139) are post graduates, 45.5% (159) have work experience of 5-10 years and 30.3% (106) earn monthly income of Rs.40,000-Rs.60,000.

Descriptive Analysis:

In order to describe the responses and understand the attitude of the respondents with respect to mean and standard deviation are calculated. While the mean shows the central tendency of the data, standard deviation measures the dispersion which offers an index of the spread or variability in the data (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). In other words, a small standard deviation for a set of values reveals that these values are clustered closely about the mean or located close to it. A large standard deviation indicates the opposite. The level of each

item was determined by the following formula: (highest point in Likert scale - lowest point in Likert scale) / the number of the levels used = $(5-1) / 5 = 0.80$, where 1-1.80 reflected “very low”, 1.81-2.60 reflected “low”, 2.61-3.40 reflected “moderate”, 3.41-4.20 reflected “high”, and 4.21-5 reflected “very high”. Then the items are being ordered based on their means. Tables (1) to (3) depict the results.

Table No. 1: Career Competency - Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation

S.No	Statements	Mean	SD	Level	Order
Reflection on Motivation					
1	I know what I like in my work	4.56	0.53	Very High	1
2	I know what is important to me in my career	4.41	0.59	Very High	2
3	I can clearly see what my passions are in my work	4.33	0.69	Very High	3
		4.43			
Reflection on Qualities					
4	I know my strengths in my work	4.48	0.58	Very High	1
5	I am familiar with my shortcomings in my work	4.08	0.72	High	3
6	I am aware of my talents in my work	4.35	0.67	Very High	2
		4.30			
Networking					
7	I know a lot people within my work who can help me with my career	3.87	0.95	High	2
8	I know a lot people outside of my work who can help me with my career	3.59	1.03	High	3
9	I am able to approach the right persons to help me with my career	3.94	0.85	High	1
		3.80			
Self-Profiling					
10	I can clearly show others what my strengths are in my work	4.35	0.57	Very High	1
11	I am able to show others what I want to achieve in my career	4.07	0.80	High	3
12	I can show the people around me what is important to me in my work	4.16	0.74	High	2
		4.20			
Work Exploration					
13	I know how to find out what my opinions are for development of my career	3.98	0.78	High	2
14	I know how to search for developments in my area of work	4.04	0.75	High	1
15	I am able to explore opportunities in the market	3.92	0.84	High	3
		3.98			
Career Control					
16	I can make clear career plans	3.92	0.76	High	2
17	I know what I want to achieve in my career	4.15	0.78	High	1
18	I am able to set goals for myself that I want to achieve in my career	4.15	0.71	High	1
		4.07			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

Out of the six factors which measured Career Competency, 'Reflection on Motivation' has emerged as the most important factor (4.43) followed by 'Reflection on Qualities' (4.30), Self-Profiling (4.20), Career Control (4.07), Work Exploration (3.98) and Networking (3.80).

As far as the first factor '**Reflection on Motivation**' is concerned, the respondents are aware what they like in their work (4.56) and what are important for their career (4.41). The second important factor is '**Reflection on Qualities**' when the respondents opine that they knew their strengths (4.48) and are aware of their talent in their work (4.35). With regards, to '**Networking**', the respondents feel that they can approach the right persons to help them with their career (3.94) since they know a lot of people within the organization (3.87) and also outside the organization (3.59). As regards '**Self-Profiling**', they are confident that they can showcase their work strengths (4.35) and what is important in their work to others (4.16). With regard to '**Work Exploration**' and '**Career Control**' they opine that they know how to search for their development (4.04), are clear what they want to achieve in their career and are capable of setting goals to achieve it (4.15).

The below table depicts the weighted mean score of the second independent factor Self-Efficacy.

Table No.2: Self-Efficacy - Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation

S.No.	Statements	Wt. Mean	SD	Level	Order
1	I always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough	4.29	0.66	Very High	1
2	If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want	3.92	0.84	High	4
3	I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events	3.96	0.67	High	3
4	I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping	3.83	0.82	High	5
5	Even if I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution	4.05	0.78	High	2
		4.01			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

Five statements were used to measure Self-Efficacy and their weighted mean scores range from 3.83 to 4.29. The respondents feel that they are able to solve even the difficult problems if they try hard (4.29), can think of solutions even in trouble (4.05), and are confident of dealing efficiently with unexpected events (3.96) in a calm manner (3.83).

The below table depicts the weighted mean scores of three kinds of Organisational Commitment measured using nine statements.

Table No.3: Organizational Commitment- Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation

S. No.	Statements	Wt. Mean	SD	Level	Order
	Affective Commitment				
1	I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career in this organisation	3.75	0.99	High	2
2	I really feel as if this organisation's problems are my own	3.56	0.97	High	3
3	I feel a strong sense of belonging to my organisation	3.91	0.83	High	1
		3.74			
	Continuance Commitment				
4	It would be hard for me to leave my job from this organisation right now even if I wanted to	3.76	1.06	High	2
5	Right now, staying with my job at this organisation is a matter of necessity as much as my desire	3.85	0.97	High	1
6	I believe I have very few alternatives elsewhere to consider leaving this organisation	3.11	1.15	Moderate	3
		3.57			
	Normative Commitment				
7	I would not leave my organisation right now because of my sense of obligation to it	3.73	0.86	High	2
8	I owe a great deal to my organisation	3.79	0.90	High	1
9	Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave my organisation	3.49	1.09	High	3
		3.67			

Source: Primary Data

Organizational Commitment was measured using three factors namely Affective Commitment, Continuance Commitment and Normative Commitment with three statements for each. Affective Commitment (3.74) has emerged as the most important commitment followed by Normative Commitment (3.67) and Continuance Commitment (3.57).

The respondents opine that they feel a strong sense of belonging towards their organization (3.91) and are happy to spend the rest of their career in the same organization (3.75). They agree that they owe a great deal to their organization (3.79) and so will not leave their organization (3.73). Staying in their current job is a necessity and desire also (3.85) and it will hard for them to leave their organization (3.76) even if they wanted to.

The next part of analysis examines the significant difference between male and female with respect to Organisational Commitment for which t test have been adopted and the results are tabulated below:

HYPOTHESIS I:

Null Hypothesis (H01): There is no significant difference between male and female respondents with respect to Organisational Commitment of the respondents.

Table No.4: Organisational Commitment and Gender – t test

Organizational Commitment	Gender				t value	P value
	Male		Female			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Affective Commitment	3.63	0.75	3.71	0.72	3.450	0.01**
Continuance Commitment	3.54	0.84	3.64	0.70	2.137	0.03*
Normative Commitment	3.62	0.76	3.72	0.81	2.214	0.02*

Source: Primary Data

The study found significant results at 1% for Affective Commitment ($t = 3.450$) and at 5% for Continuance Commitment ($t = 2.137$) and Normative Commitment ($t = 2.214$). Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that significant differences exist between male and female employees with respect to Organisational Commitment.

The next part of analysis examines the significant group difference among the respondents with respect to Organisational Commitment based on chosen demographics for which ANOVA values are tabulated below from Table No.5 to Table No.7:

HYPOTHESIS II:

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among the respondents of different age groups with respect to Organisational Commitment.

Table No.5: Organisational Commitment and Age Groups (ANOVA)

Organisational Commitment	Age (in years)				F Value	p Value
	25-35	35-45	45-55	Above 55		
Affective Commitment	3.60 (0.72)	3.70 (0.77)	4.11 (0.62)	4.22 (0.44)	8.275	0.000**
Continuance Commitment	3.47 (0.73)	3.54 (0.81)	3.93 (0.69)	3.77 (0.59)	4.806	0.003*
Normative Commitment	3.50 (0.72)	3.60 (0.81)0	4.16 (0.61)	4.77 (0.33)	9.115	0.000**

Source: Primary Data

Note: 1. The value within bracket refers to standard deviation

2. ** denotes significance at 1% level

3. * denotes significance at 5% level

Interpretation:

The above table clearly indicates that there exists significant difference among the respondents of different age groups at 1% level of significance since the p value is less than 0.01, with respect to the Affective Commitment and Normative Commitment and Continuance Commitment at 5% level of significance thereby resulting in the rejection of second null hypothesis. As the age of the respondents increase, they feel a strong sense of belonging towards their organization (since weighted mean scores of age group 45-55 years and above 55 years are higher) and they stay in their organization as much as their desire, they owe a great deal to their organization and it would be difficult for them to leave their organization even if they wanted to do.

HYPOTHESIS III:

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among respondents with varying years of work experience with respect to Organisational Commitment

Table No.6 Organisational Commitment and Years of Work Experience (ANOVA)

Organisational Commitment	Experience in years				F Value	p Value
	Below 5	5-10	10-15	15-20		
Affective Commitment	3.58 (0.71)	3.73 (0.83)	3.93 (0.72)	3.94 (0.64)	5.355	0.000**
Continuance Commitment	3.49 (0.68)	3.61 (0.78)	3.45 (0.93)	3.83 (0.76)	3.663	0.013*
Normative Commitment	3.60 (0.72)	3.62 (0.85)	3.63 (0.82)	3.89 (0.83)	2.186	0.089

Source: Primary Data

Note: 1. The value within bracket refers to standard deviation

2.** denotes significance at 1% level

3. * denotes significance at 5% level

Interpretation:

The above table clearly states that there exists significant difference among the respondents with varying years of work experience at 1% level for Affective Commitment and at 5% for Continuance Commitment thereby resulting in the rejection of third null hypothesis. As the years of work experience increases, the level of their affective commitment and continuance commitment also increases. The respondents also feel that their organization's problems are their own problems, continuing in their organization is a desire for them and they believe that there are very few alternatives available elsewhere even if they want to leave.

HYPOTHESIS IV:

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference among the respondents belonging to different income groups with respect to Organisational Commitment.

Table No.7: Organisational Commitment and Monthly Income (ANOVA)

Organisational Commitment	Monthly Income (in Rs)				F Value	p Value
	Below Rs.20,000	Rs.20,000- Rs.40,000	Rs.40,000- Rs.60,000	Above Rs.60,000		
Affective Commitment	3.51 (0.67)	3.89 (0.71)	3.60 (0.75)	3.89 (0.74)	6.116	0.000**
Continuance Commitment	3.48 (0.58)	3.85 (0.74)	3.47 (0.68)	3.42 (0.96)	6.334	0.000**
Normative Commitment	3.58 (0.63)	3.88 (0.77)	3.57 (0.82)	3.60 (0.83)	3.376	0.019*

Source: Primary Data

Note: 1. The value within bracket refers to standard deviation

2. ** denotes significance at 1% level

3. * denotes significance at 5% level

Interpretation:

The above table clearly states that there exists significant difference among the respondents belonging to the different income groups at 1% level for Affective and Continuance Commitment and since the p value is less than 0.01 and at 5% level for Normative Commitment thereby resulting in the rejection of fourth null hypothesis. The respondents feel that they will not leave their organization because of their sense of obligation and they are happy to spend the rest of their career in the same organization. Staying in their current job is a necessity and desire also and it will be hard for them to leave their organization even if they wanted to.

13. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The weighted mean results revealed that out of the six factors of Career Competency, 'Reflection on Motivation' has emerged as the most important factor followed by 'Reflection on Qualities' t test results revealed that female respondents were more committed to their organization than the male employees. ANOVA results state that there exists significant difference among the respondents based on the chosen demographic variable namely age, years of work experience and monthly income with respect to three factors of Organizational Commitment (Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment).

14. CONCLUSION:

The study recommends that for an organization to achieve an increase in organisational commitment, innovation, high market share, and long-term survival, it must involve in building the career competency abilities of their employees. Managers should engage in the exploitation of current organizational capabilities

and exploration of future opportunities to create, maintain, and sustain a competitive position. This study suggests the best way for an organisation to retain its employees is by promoting the development of their key competencies, which is in line with Reiche (2008). When employees feel that the organisation is concerned with the development of their career competencies, their perception of internal employability will be higher (Cesário et al. 2012), making them feel more committed to the organisation where they work (Meyer and Smith 2000), and decreasing their intentions to voluntarily leave (Meyer and Allen 1991).

15. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY:

This study will help to understand the need to build career competency, self-efficacy of individuals and involve organizations in providing support to their employees in managing their careers. It will add to the existing body of knowledge and help the employers to understand how they should keep their employees engaged and increase their level of organisational commitment which will result in increased production and can affect recruitment, retention and profitability in a positive way. It will help to foster individuals' competency skills which results in enhanced organisational commitment. Workshops oriented at clarifying and communicating organizational values, philosophy and principles can be all beneficial for strengthening employees' commitment to the organization. The study will help future researchers to conduct further research on the relevant topic and explore it further in an effective way.

16. LIMITATIONS / RESTRICTIONS OF THE STUDY:

Different findings could be obtained from broader samples from different sectors. Only two predictors of organisational commitment have been considered for the present study.

17. SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH :

Future studies can be done by considering other independent variables such as loyalty, competency mapping, and job satisfaction in predicting organisational commitment. A mediating or a moderator variable can be introduced between the independent variables (career competency and self-efficacy) and the dependent variable (Organisational Commitment) and the results can be recorded. Future researches in this area can use an experimental design to explore the causal relationship between the variables. Future researches can also take a broader and a more representative sample from across many sectors. A comparative study also can also be made between the service and manufacturing industries and their level of organisational commitment can be assessed.

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